

Ramachandran Plot

saves

Plot statistics

Residues in most favoured regions [A,B,L]	212	85.5%
Residues in additional allowed regions [a,b,l,p]	36	14.5%
Residues in generously allowed regions [~a,~b,~l,~p]	0	0.0%
Residues in disallowed regions	0	0.0%

Number of non-glycine and non-proline residues	248	100.0%
Number of end-residues (excl. Gly and Pro)	7	
Number of glycine residues (shown as triangles)	19	
Number of proline residues	14	

Total number of residues	288	

Based on an analysis of 118 structures of resolution of at least 2.0 Angstroms and R-factor no greater than 20%, a good quality model would be expected to have over 90% in the most favoured regions.